

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON THE SALE OF PARLE-G BISCUITS

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Abstract:

We all have grown enjoying Parle-G biscuits with tea or milk, and it has been a common choice for all since 1938. While the market is flooded with many choices, there is something unique about this pocket-friendly biscuit that we end up using for exotic tarts and no-bake cakes too. During the lockdown, the company achieved a unique feat of selling the largest number of biscuit packets during the pandemic. The company had grown overall market share by nearly 5%... And 80– 90% of this growth has come from the Parle-G sales. This is unprecedented. It is believed that during the national lockdown the sales of fairly priced biscuits spiked as people stacked up on easy and simple essential food items. This is a common man's biscuit; people who cannot afford bread – buy Parle-G. In this research paper researcher is trying to show the positive impact of covid-19 on the growth rate of Parle Company just by selling their Parle-G biscuits.

Keywords: *Pandemic, Covid-19, Market share etc.*

Introduction

- The first Parle product was the iconic orange candy which is still popular till now. During the British period, biscuits were luxury products and were only produced and consumed by the elite class.
- The biscuits were imported from other countries, mostly British. The company was mastering in the world of confectioneries and toffees.
- During the crisis of World War 2, the first Parle G biscuit was produced in 1939. In the beginning, its name was Parle Gluco.
- This wheat made biscuit is of very affordable price and the majority of Indian people can buy this biscuit easily.
- Parle Gluco was by the Indians and for the Indians.
- They were much in demand by the British-Indian army during the second world war.
- The *Parle Gluco* biscuit become very popular at that time and its capture all the market very easily.
- All British companies started losing at that time. After the end of the second world war, *Parle Gluco* had become a big brand.
- In 1947, the production of the biscuits had stopped for a brief time due to the shortage of wheat after India's independence.
- They produced barley biscuits until the supplies for wheat were restored. After the production was stopped, people started scarcity of Parle biscuit and this was realized by the company soon and they promise to start the production soon.

- In 1982 Parle Gluco is changed to Parle G as the company does not have a patent on the Gluco word. So other companies in the market start taking advantage of Gluco or Glucose word and start using it at the end of their biscuits name.
- Due to this, parle sale was very influenced. This is the main reason behind changing the parle gluco biscuit name.
- As of today, there are 400 million Parle G biscuits being produced daily. 14,600 crore biscuit packets are sold every year

Objectives of the study:

- To study the growth performance of the Parle G biscuits
- To study the marketing strategies of the Parle Company during their business times.
- To study the impact of pandemic situation on sale of Parle G biscuits.

Need of the study:

- In present situation how one can grow our business?
- What kind of strategies as a company they can apply?
- In what way one can stick in competition?
- To find the answers of this question there is a need to study such examples.

Research Methodology:

Secondary Data: The data is collected based on Secondary sources has been collected from published Books, Magazines, Reports, relevant websites and records of government agencies.

Findings of the study:

- Leading food company Parle Products logged record sales of its Parle-G biscuits in April and May during the lockdown, said a senior company official.
- The company has gained a market share of around 5% in the highly competitive biscuit segment, helped by Parle-G biscuits, preferred by the people stocking up their pantries during the pandemic.
- Parle-G biscuits also gained traction as it was preferred by government agencies and NGOs working to distribute food relief packages to people during the pandemic owing to its economic proposition with value package of ₹2 besides being considered a good source of glucose, Parle Products senior category head.
- The growth was phenomenal and as a result Parle was able to increase its market share by 4.5 to 5% during the lockdown.
- **This is one of the highest in the recent (time).**
- **Parle-G was comfort food for most Indians and that during times of uncertainty, it was consumed a lot. Even during earlier crises like tsunami and earthquakes, sales of Parle-G biscuits had gone up.**
- **That is the kind of trust people deposit in the brand Parle-G's long shelf life as another reason for the preference.**
- **The company would donate three crore packs of Parle-G biscuits when the coronavirus pandemic intensified in India.**
- **There were many other organisations, which were also helping people by distributing Parle-G biscuits.**

	Mar'20	Mar'19	Mar'18	Mar'17	Mar'16
	12Months	12Months	12Months	12Months	12Months
INCOME:					
Sales Turnover	5.49	11.35	.17	.27	.24
Excise Duty	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
NET SALES	5.49	11.35	.17	.27	.24
Other Income	0.3896	0.0008	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
TOTAL INCOME	5.88	11.35	.17	.27	.24

Conclusion:

Fast-moving consumer goods maker Parle Products recorded a surge in sales of its Parle-G biscuits during the coronavirus-induced lockdown, backed by strong demand for the ₹ 5 packs during March through May.

The demand for Parle-G was boosted as the biscuits came handy for people working from home as well as migrant workers returning to their homes during the nationwide lockdown which began on March 25. The jump in sales is good news for the country's largest biscuit maker, which had last year warned it might trim production as well as workforce amid slowing economic growth and falling demand

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